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Ultrafiltration process in the mechanized production of Shrikhand, a fermented dairy product

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Introduction: Membrane processing is a green technology serving as a viable alternative to many traditional dairy processes like distillation, evaporation or extraction (1). Shrikhand is a popular Indian dessert from milk popular in western Indian states of Gujarat and Maharashtra. Traditionally it is prepared from cow or buffalo milk curd or dahi. The curd is hung to get a semi-solid mass called chakka, which is blended with required amount of sugar, colour and flavorings to a smooth and homogenous consistency (2). The process is tedious consuming about 22 hours, giving a lower yield and involving less mechanization. The present study is proposed to utilize ultrafiltered and diafiltered whole milk retentate to make shrikhand. The membrane module used was spiral wound type made of polyethersulphone having a molecular weight cut-off (MWCO) of 10,000 Daltons and surface area of 5.57m² procured from PMI process systems, Bangalore. Operation was in batch mode.

Methods: Ultrafiltration of standardized whole milk was done at different temperature-transmembrane pressure combinations of 45/50/55°C and 0.3/0.4/0.5 MPa for optimization with respect to the membrane used by measuring the permeate flux. Concentration of milk was done at 3,4 and 5 levels of concentration factors. The retentate and permeate were analyzed for the rejection factors of the major components for optimization of the concentration factor. The retentate was used to make shrikhand. The physico-chemical and sensory properties of the product were compared with the control sample prepared by traditional method.

Results & Discussions: The processing parameters of the membrane were optimized at 50°C, 0.4 MPa transmembrane pressure and a concentration factor of 3. Ultrafiltered whole milk shrikhand was on par with the control in sensory attributes as evaluated by a panel of trained judges based on 9-point hedonic scale. Diafiltered shrikhand had low acidity and dull colour due to the removal of most of the lactose in the permeate. There was no significant difference between the control and ultrafiltered sample though the control was adjudged the best. The treatments had higher yield (25% more than the control) due to the incorporation of highly nutritive whey proteins, which are otherwise lost in whey. The production time was reduced to 8 hours. The microbiological quality of the mechanized product was also high. Results were analyzed using Completely Randomized Design (CRD) using three replications.

Conclusions: The study demonstrates the suitability of membrane technology in shrikhand preparation. The distinct advantages include improved yield, enhanced nutritive value and uniform product without sacrificing the sensory qualities of the final product.

Keywords: Membrane process, dairy, ultrafiltration, diafiltration, shrikhand, mechanization

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